

Synthetic Studies in the Indole Field. Part VII. Synthesis of Indole-2-aldehydes

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The McFadyen-Stevens method for the preparation of indole-2-aldehydes from the corresponding ethyl indole-2-carboxylates has been studied and several members of the group have been synthesised thereby.

Indole-3-aldehydes are obtained from the corresponding indoles in very high yields according to the method of Smith¹. Indole-2-aldehydes, on the other hand, are not easily accessible. Indole-2-aldehyde was prepared in rather a poor yield by Taylor² by reducing 2-ethoxycarbonylindole with lithium aluminium hydride and oxidising the resulting alcohol with potassium permanganate in acetone. An improved method of preparation of indole-2-aldehyde has recently been reported by Harley-Mason and Pavri³, employing activated manganese dioxide to oxidise 2-hydroxymethylindole.

Brown *et al.*⁴ employed the McFadyen and Stevens general procedure for the synthesis of various Bz-formylindoles. During the course of some work on benzindoles in this laboratory, 3-methyl-4,5-benzindole-2-carboxyaldehyde and 3-methyl-6,7-benzindole-2-carboxyaldehyde were obtained in high yields from the corresponding 2-ethoxycarbonyl-benzindoles by the McFadyen and Stevens procedure. In view of this, we undertook to investigate further the utility of the McFadyen and Stevens method for the preparation of various indole-2-aldehydes required as starting materials for the synthesis of 2-isotryptamines.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3842.

2. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 33, 164.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2665.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1843.

The appropriate indole-2-carboxylic ester (I) was allowed to react with hydrazine hydrate (100%) to obtain the carbohydrazide (II) which was converted into the *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative (III). Compound (III) was decomposed with anhydrous sodium carbonate in ethylene glycol to obtain the corresponding indole-2-aldehyde (IV). The indole 2-aldehydes (IV, a-d) have been synthesised by employing this procedure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5-methylindole-2-carboxylate⁵ (Ia) and ethyl 7-methylindole-2-carboxylate (Ib) were respectively prepared from ethyl pyruvate 5-methyl- and -7-methyl-phenylhydrazone⁶ by the Fischer method, using ethanolic HCl as the cyclising agent.

Ethyl 3,5-dimethylindole-2-carboxylate (Ic) and ethyl 3,7-dimethylindole-2-carboxylate⁶ (Id) were prepared respectively from ethyl α -ketobutyrate *p*-methyl- and -*o*-methyl-phenylhydrazone by the Fischer method, using ethanolic H₂SO₄ as the cyclising agent.

Indole-2-carbohydrazides(II)

Ethyl 5-methylindole-2-carboxylate (2.5 g.), hydrazine hydrate (100 %, 5 ml), and anhydrous ethanol (25 ml) were heated under reflux on a steam bath for 5 hr. On cooling the mixture, the hydrazide crystallised as colorless needles, which were collected, washed with ethanol, and recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The various indole-2-carbohydrazides, similarly prepared, are described in Table I.

TABLE I

2-Carbohydrazides.	Crystal shape.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
(IIa) 5-Methylindole-	Colorless needles	240-50°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ON ₃	22.73	22.22
(IIb) 7-Methylindole-	Yellow plates	261-62°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ON ₃	22.03	22.22
(IIc) 3,5-Dimethylindole-	Yellow prisms	264-65°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₃	20.01	20.68
(IId) 3,7-Dimethylindole-	Yellow flakes	245-46°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₃	20.62	20.68

2-Toluene-p-sulphonhydrazidocarbonylindoles (III)

To 5-methylindole-2-carbohydrazide (2.5 g.), dissolved in freshly distilled pyridine (30 ml) and cooled in an ice bath, *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.4 g.) was added in small portions with constant shaking. The reaction mixture after keeping in an ice bath for 1hr. and then at the room temperature for another hour was then poured into ice containing HCl (conc., 25 ml). The solid separating was collected and washed with HCl (dil.) and water. The crude 5-methyl-2-toluene-*p*-sulphonhydrazidocarbonylindole was crystallised from anhydrous ethanol.

5. Robson, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, **62**, 495.

6. Carlin *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 5712.

The various toluene-*p*-sulphonhydrazidocarbonylindoles, similarly prepared, are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Substituted (X) 2-toluene-p-sulphonhydrazidocarbonylindoles (III).

S.No.	X.	Crystal shape.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
IIIa	5-Methyl-	Buff needles	251-52°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	12.50	12.25
IIIb	7-Methyl-	Do	220-21°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	11.87	12.25
III c	3,5-Dimethyl-	Do	236-37°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	12.18	11.76
III d	3,7-Dimethyl-	Yellowish brown plates	243-44°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	12.12	11.76

Indole-2-aldehydes (IV) from (III)

5-Methyl-2-toluene-*p*-sulphonhydrazidocarbonylindole (2.5 g.) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) was heated to 160° in an oil bath to dissolve it and to the boiling solution anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.5 g.) was added. After allowing 5 minutes for reaction, the mixture was poured on crushed ice (500 g.) and allowed to stand for 1 hr. 5-Methylindole-2-aldehyde separating as a solid was collected and purified by crystallisation from ethanol. The various indole-2-aldehydes, similarly prepared, and their derivatives are described in Table III.

TABLE III

Indole-2-carboxyaldehydes (IV) and their derivatives.

S.No.	2-Carboxyaldehydes.	Crystal shape.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
IV a	5-Methylindole-	Light yellow plates	175-76°	90	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON	8.94	8.80
	(a) 2, 4-DNP	Reddish brown granules	285-86°	..	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	20.63	20.65
IV b	7-Methylindole-	Yellow granules	190-91°	45	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON	8.42	8.80
	(b) 2,4-DNP	Brown prisms	265-86°	..	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	20.39	20.65
IV c	3, 5-Dimethylindole-	Do	140-41°	90	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON	7.55	8.09
	(c) 2, 4-DNP	Reddish brown needles	315-16°	..	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	19.75	19.83
IV d	3, 7-Dimethylindole-	Yellow granules	138-39°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON	8.14	8.09
	(d) 2,4-DNP	Reddish brown needles	276-77°	..	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	19.87	19.83

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